

ANALYSIS OF THE ECONOMY OF THE SERVICE SECTOR AND THE CONDITIONS CREATED FOR ITS DEVELOPMENT

Karimov Oybek Olimjon ugli

Student of Namangan State Technical University

Tel: +998975701405

E-mail: karimovojbek353@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15266947>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 29-yanvar 2025 yil

Ma'qullandi: 10-fevral 2025yil

Nashr qilindi: 25-fevral 2025 yil

KEYWORDS

Local producers, gross domestic product, digital economy, service sector, service provision, social sphere, consulting services, market services, international experience, private sector, small business.

ABSTRACT

The service sector is an important sector of the economy, performing economic and social activities for society and individuals. The article examines the economic analysis of the service sector, its importance, types and opportunities created for the development of the sector. Using economic and statistical methods, an analysis of the main indicators of the service sector by type of activity and its share in GDP was conducted.

Introduction The level of development of the service sector has become a determining factor in ensuring a high quality of life for the population and accelerating economic growth. The incomparable importance of this sector, especially in solving the problem of providing employment for the working population and increasing their income, should be recognized as a great achievement of human society. Increasing the role of the sector in raising the standard and quality of life of the population requires, first of all, a thorough analysis of the current state and development trends of this sector, identifying existing problems in this area and finding ways to solve them, identifying opportunities and their effective use in the future. By the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 No. PF-60 "On the Development Strategy of the New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" dated January 28, 2022 No. 34 Appendix 1: "Development of the system of engineering, communications and social infrastructure of the regions, as well as the service sector and service" [1] the following tasks are set: Increase the volume of services provided by 3 times in the next 5 years due to the development of the service sector and service in the regions and create a total of 3.5 million new jobs in this area. Develop paid service points in city and regional centers: plumbing, electrical engineering, household appliance repair, catering establishments, develop household and communal services that meet the daily needs of the population. To create 130 modern markets and shopping malls, as well as 65 large and 5,000 small service facilities for the development of roadside infrastructure in the regions of the republic through the development of trade and roadside service. To reduce the share of the shadow economy in the service sector by 3 times. To increase the attractiveness of the service sector, provide additional benefits to enterprises in this sector. The above information indicates that in the context of the current global crisis, one of the most pressing issues today is to stimulate further state support for the service sector in Uzbekistan, improve the business environment through further development of infrastructure, and develop scientific recommendations and proposals to identify and eliminate problems arising in these processes. An important component of the national economy of the country is the service sector. The service sector plays a leading role in the socio-economic development of the country, in particular, in the formation of GDP, ensuring employment of the population, satisfying its various needs, improving the standard and quality of life, and forming the state budget. At the same time, the service sector is a multidisciplinary industry operating in several directions at once.

In this area, complex socio-economic processes are constantly occurring and developing, which are inextricably linked with other sectors of the national economy. The service sector, on the one hand, has a significant impact on other sectors and branches of the national economy, their state and

development, and on the other hand, the possibilities and prospects for its development are determined by the dynamics of other sectors and industries. LITERATURE REVIEW Scientific research and development on this topic was and is being conducted by domestic and foreign scientists who contribute to the development of this area. "The great economist Adam Smith, in order to most fully reveal the economic content of service goods and solve the problem of considering them as a source of social wealth of the country, expressed his views on the concepts of productive labor and unproductive labor in his world-famous work "An Inquiry into the Nature and Causes of the Wealth of Nations" [2]. Thus, A. Smith made a significant contribution to the creation of the original concept of service, distinguishing between tangible and intangible products. The term service is used by scientists in economic literature from different positions and is interpreted depending on the field of economic knowledge. Many foreign and domestic scientists have conducted theoretical studies within the framework of this term. One of the famous scientists is F. Kotler, who defines a service as follows: "A service is any activity that one party can offer to another" [3]. One of the prominent scientists of our republic I.S. Tukhliev says: "Services are a special type of intangible goods" [4] and in this approach the scientist tries to emphasize that services are goods by their nature, that is, they reflect labor relations in the processes of production and material production, but the result of the production process has an intangible form. The definition of the concept of service given by I. Ochilov is more complete in content and essence than others, and is given in the following form: "When we talk about a service, we mean the conscious activity of people associated with the process of providing a service that brings benefits aimed at satisfying a certain need of a person, economic entities, the state and society" [5]. Mukhamedov emphasizes that the service sector has a direct and significant impact on health, mood, attitude to work, productivity of workers, level of satisfaction and happiness with life, and in general on life and development of productive forces. In particular, in this regard, domestic scientists M.K. Pardaev and H.N. Musaev argue that "the service sector is an integral part of the market economy and participates in the general system of economic relations" [6]. A striking example of this are the definitions "...". Successful solution of the priority tasks outlined in the Development Strategy "Uzbekistan-2030" requires the development of specific measures to provide quality services to the population of our republic by increasing the economic efficiency of the service sector, improving the system of statistical indicators, statistical forecasting of its prospects.

Research Methodology. The information in the article was analyzed in a comparative manner and an attempt was made to theoretically illuminate the types of services, their economic importance, the development of the service sector and the opportunities created for the development of the sector. In the process of scientific analysis, the methods of observation, generalization, grouping, comparison, synthesis and analysis were widely used. The types of services were considered as the object of the study.

Analysis and discussion of the results. The service sector occupies a leading place among the main areas of development of the modern economy. This is a complex multifaceted mechanism and one of the promising sectors of the modern economy, covering a wide range of activities: from trade and transport to education and insurance services. The diversity of activities in the service sector, as well as the relationship between different types of activities in the service sector, serve as a factor in the rapid development of this sector. The measures taken to balance domestic demand and comprehensively support the development of local producers ensure a change in the structure of consumer demand. In recent years, a number of opportunities have been created for business entities operating in the service sector, as well as for increasing their share in the country's gross domestic product. In our country, types of services based on high technologies and characteristic of a market economy are rapidly developing. The new Development Strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 defines specific measures for the development of the service sector, including such important tasks as "implementation of target programs for the construction of affordable housing, development and modernization of road, transport, engineering and communications and social infrastructure" [8]. According to preliminary data of the Statistics Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2023, the volume of services reached 470,286.5 billion soums, and the share of small businesses in this area was 47.7%, the volume of services per capita was 12,915.6 thousand soums, and the share of enterprises and organizations was 70.7%. At the end of 2023, the share of the service sector in GDP increased from 41.6% to 43.4%. At the same time, the share of agriculture, forestry and fisheries decreased from 24.9% to 24.3%, the share of industry - from 27.0% to 26.1%, and the share

of the construction sector - from 6.5% to 6.2%. In 2023, GDP per capita amounted to 29,291.4 thousand soums in current prices. If we analyze the contribution of types of services to the growth of the total volume of market services provided for 2019-2023, we can see that financial services increased by 4.5%, trade services - by 2.5%, transport services - by 1.8%, other services - by 1.8%, communication and information services - by 1.6%, education services - by 1.0%, accommodation and food services - by 0.5%, that is, this indicator increased by 13.7% over these periods. If we compare these indicators, that is, the growth of these market services, with the preliminary data for 2023 compared to the same period in 2022, we can see that trade services grew by 23.5%, transport services - by 23.1%, financial services - by 22.6%, communication and information services - by 6.9%, educational services - by 4.3%, accommodation and food services - by 3.9%, as well as services related to real estate - by 2.6%, healthcare services - by 1.8%, rental services - by 1.6%, services in the field of architecture, engineering surveys, technical testing and analysis - by 1.7%, other services - by 4.2%. The analysis shows that according to preliminary data for 2023, if we statistically consider the composition of market services rendered by types of economic activity, the largest share in the composition of market services rendered by types of economic activity is occupied by trade services (23.5%) and transport services (23.1%). If we analyze the services sector by types of activity, then in the total volume of transport services in 2023, the predominant share will be automobile transport services - 47.3%. The largest share in the total volume of communication and information services is occupied by telecommunications services. In 2023, the share of this sector was 54.7 percent. The share of services in the educational sector was 56.5 percent. In 2023, the share of hospital services will account for a significant share of the total volume of healthcare services. Their share was 43.1 percent.

Conclusion and suggestions. In conclusion, it should be said that today the service sector is one of the most important sectors of the modern national economy. This sector is not limited to traditional activities, it is constantly expanding its participation in the life of society, is integrated into social production, and is also connected by specific ties with almost all sectors of the economy. "The Development Strategy of the New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" sets many goals and objectives. Based on these defined goals and objectives, it is necessary to continue the continuity of these reforms, in particular, the systematic development of the service sector in the future. Therefore, we consider it appropriate to make a number of proposals for the development of this sector in the current conditions of the digital economy. Based on the goals and objectives set, it is necessary to continue the continuity of these reforms, in particular, the systematic development of the service sector in the future. Therefore, we consider it appropriate to make a number of proposals for the development of this sector in the current period of new economic development. Firstly, to expand the scope of modern market services, to create a positive competitive environment in the industry through the introduction of new types of services, and to sharply increase the share of the industry in the country's national economy. This requires further improvement of the efficiency of the service sector and its transformation into a driver of the economy. Secondly, to widely attract foreign investors and the private sector to this area and expand their activities in order to develop IT, education, tourism, communications, transport and logistics services, increase the level of access to the Internet in remote areas and improve quality indicators, adapt the roadside service infrastructure to modern requirements, and effectively use empty buildings and land in the healthcare system.

LIST OF REFERENCES:

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2022 yil 28 yanvardagi "2022—2026 yillarda Yangi O'zbekistonning taraqqiyot strategiyasi to'g'risida"gi farmoni. // www.lex.uz
2. Kotler, F., Marketing management. Express courses. 2nd edition. / Translated into English. Redacted. Bojuk SG St. Petersburg: Piter, 2006.- 464 pages.
3. Tuxliyev IS, Hayitboyev R., Ibodullayev N.YE., Amriddinova RS Turizm asoslari: O'quv qo'llanma – S.: SamISI, 2010 - 247 bet.
4. Ochilov I. Bozor munosabatlari sharoitida xizmatlarning turlari va ularning tavsifi. // Xizmat ko'rsatish, servis va turizm sohalarini rivojlantirish: muammolar va ularning yechimlari. Monografiya. T.: "IQTISODIYOT-MOLIYA", 2008 yil.
5. Mualliflar jamoasi. Xizmat ko'rsatish, servis va turizm sohalarini rivojlantirish: muammolar va ularning yechimlari. Monografiya. Professorlar MQPardayev va HNMusayevlar tahriri ostida - T.: Iqtisod-moliya, 2008. - 194 bet.

6. Farmon (2023) O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Sh.M.Mipziyoyevning 2023 yil 11 sentabrdagi "O'zbekiston - 2030" strategiyasi to'g'risida"gi PF-158-sonli Farmoni. // www.lex.uz
7. Qaror, (2022) O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2022 yil 27 yanvardagi "Xizmatlar sohasini rivojlantirishga oid qo'shimcha chora-tadbirlar to'g'risida"gi PQ 104-sonli qarori. // <https://lex.uz/docs/584028>

